

CONSERVATION AND MANAGEMENT

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Preliminary studies on alpha taxonomy of hymenopteran pollinators (Family: Vespidae, Sphecidae, Scoliidae and Pompilidae) in Malappuram and Kozhikode districts, Kerala, India.

Kalathinga Thodi Fahis** & Karikkuzhi Palliyali Mohammed Shareef **

*Centre for Conservation Ecology and Department of Zoology, MES Mampad College (Autonomous), Malappuram, Kerala, India-676542

**P.G. & Research Department of Zoology, P.S.M.O. College, Tirurangadi, Malappuram, Kerala, India-676306

Presenting author: fahis1910@gmail.com

Wasps are excellent pollinators that play crucial roles in ecosystems. They are predators of almost all insect larvae, which threaten crops, agriculture, and forests. This study focuses on the biosystematics of vespid, sphecid, scoliid, and pompilid wasps found in the selected regions of the Malappuram and Kozhikode districts of Kerala from September 2020 to May 2021. A checklist of 46 specimens collected from four families was prepared. Among the collected specimens, 26 species were from three families, one unidentified species was from Scolia of Scoliidae, and two unidentified specimens were from Pompilidae. Vespidae was dominant with 18 species, followed by Sphecidae, Scoliidae, and Pompilidae. Vespids belonging to 11 genera in three subfamilies, Eumeninae, Polistinae, and Vespinae, were reported in this study. The majority of vespid wasps have been reported belong to the subfamily Eumeninae. Vespids were mainly obtained from the Malappuram district. 66% of vespids were solitary, and the rest were colonial forms. Five species of sphecid wasps belonging to four genera in three subfamilies have been reported from the Malappuram and Kozhikode districts. The three sphecid subfamilies reported in this study are Ammophilinae, Sceliphrinae, and Sphecinae. Among the collected specimens, female wasps were dominant. Three species of scoliids belonging to two genera in the subfamily Scoliinae were identified in this study, and two pompilids were identified at the family level.

